

MetaDocencia: A Community of Practice to Teach Teaching Open and Reproducible Research

Interim Report

Note: This is not a full report. All sections with private information have been removed from this document.

Grant Overview

- Grant title: MetaDocencia: A Community of Practice to Teach Teaching Open and Reproducible Research
- Grant period: December 1, 2021 to November 30, 2023
- Date of report: November 1, 2022
- Grant purpose: To take MetaDocencia from a volunteer-based organization to a sustainable non-profit organization in the longer term.
- Project goals and milestones
 - Continue teaching technical skills for open and reproducible computational skills to Spanish-speaking researchers and instructors from Latin America and other geographies;
 - Generate new lessons and content for easy engagement for reproducibility in responsible and open science;
 - Solidify an active Latin American community of practice for open science; and
 - Nurture, guide, and inspire the development of other Global-South-centered communities of practice for open and reproducible research.

I. Project Assessment

Project goals + milestones	Year 1 deliverables	Indicators of impact	Strengths and areas for growth
<p>Continue teaching technical skills for open and reproducible computational skills to Spanish-speaking researchers and instructors from Latin America and other geographies</p>	<p>Organize 1 event every two weeks for a total of 26 events for a minimum of 15 attendees per event.</p> <p>Update of existing workshops.</p> <p>Improve event registration and certification infrastructure and procedures.</p>	<p>We organized 17 events with an average of 15 attendees per event until the end of October. Six workshops are planned and will occur until mid December.</p> <p>We are updating “Essentials to Teaching Online” and “Teaching Programming.”</p> <p>The complete redesign/update of our event registration and certification infrastructure and procedures is in progress.</p>	<p>The return to in-person activities manifests in fatigue to participate in online events. Shortening our events has proven effective to having active participation until the end of each event.</p> <p>Facilitating YouTube recordings and live interpretation of events with English-speaking presenters has also facilitated access to our events. Our content has been viewed about 2,800 times as of early September.</p>
<p>Generate new lessons and content for easy engagement for reproducibility in responsible and open science</p>	<p>Develop, pilot, and teach 2 new workshops in 2022 and 2 new workshops in 2023 (Year 2 deliverable).</p>	<p>We are currently developing the following workshops:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. “Accessible Zoom with Screen Reader” is in its piloting stage and will be published by the end of November. 2. “Online Tools for Effective Teaching” presents advanced features of several online resources catered for educators. It will be piloted and published by the end of November. 3. Ethics and Social Impacts of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is in development and will be piloted and published by March 2023. 4. How to Teach Bioinformatics is in development and will be piloted and published in 2023. 	<p>Our community is eager to receive our new content (e.g. the Ethics and Social Impacts for AI workshop has received a lot of attention due to this press piece featuring one of our instructors, who are regionally recognized as AI experts).</p> <p>Thus, to avoid any delays next year, given the availability of instructors willing to design the 4 new workshops committed as deliverables for this grant, we started the design of all 4 workshops during Year 1.</p> <p>This is allowing us to promote the workshops for next year earlier while we also pilot and launch the research project to measure and publish our impact.</p>

Project goals + milestones	Year 1 deliverables	Indicators of impact	Strengths and areas for growth
<p>Solidify an active Latin American community of practice for open science</p>	<p>Design and execute procedures for hiring and supervising staff.</p> <p>Design our governance.</p> <p>Maintain, nurture, and steward an active online community.</p>	<p>Our first open hiring process attracted a diverse pool of 142 highly-qualified candidates (~50% had PhD or more than one MS degrees mostly in Social Sciences and the Humanities). Candidates were from 11 Spanish-speaking countries.</p> <p>We are conducting a collective governance design with a team of 10 persons meeting twice a week for 4 months + 8 well-attended events open to everyone in our community. Our series of open governance meetings currently have 100 registered attendees joining from 15 countries and representing 13 communities. We are heavily documenting this process. Part of the results of this collective process is already reflected in our website.</p> <p>As of October 1st, we have 1,031 Facebook fans and 2,214, 243, 205, and 207 Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, and YouTube followers, respectively. Our Slack has 664 members (on average 44 members are active weekly). In the second semester of 2022, our views on YouTube increased by 33% (from 71 views/month to 94 views/month). Our post engagement rate (PER) increased on Twitter (from 4.2% PER to 5.5% PER) and on Facebook (from 1.2% PER to 5.9 % PER).</p>	<p>Our first hiring process was very competitive and a complete success. It allowed MetaDocencia to hire 3 extremely talented persons and to reach persons and communities that were not in contact with us before, seemingly because they could not afford to work as volunteers. 96% of our candidates got to know MetaDocencia for the first time through our hiring call and selection process, which was commended on its inclusivity and care, reflecting our values.</p> <p>Collectively designing our governance, including agreeing on our values and how to operationalize them, renewing our vision, mission, and community personas and paths, is resulting in a very strong core community and belonging culture. Our process has been recognized by several regional governance experts as innovative. We believe that all the documentation we will share about our process will provide valuable materials for other Open Science communities of practice and contribute to significantly augment the community of practice governance resources in Spanish.</p> <p>For 2023 we are creating an annual communication strategy to further</p>

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<p>Solidify an active Latin American community of practice for open science (continued)</p>	<p>Maintain, nurture, and steward an active online community (continued).</p> <p>Monthly newsletter.</p> <p>Collaboration with new open science communities and potential funders.</p> <p>Elaborate a proposal for new funding (Year 2 milestone).</p>	<p>Users visited our website over 9,335 times in 2022.</p> <p>Reflecting the changes the project went through in 2022, especially since the new hires arrived, contributions on MetaDocencia's website repository have soared. Our infrastructure, communication, and accessibility teams thoroughly reviewed content and design. We expect to reach the 1,000th GitHub commit before 2023.</p> <p>Our newsletter was very well received by 1,922 Spanish-speaking persons in our community with an opening rate of 39%. We translated it to English for further international reach.</p> <p>We started working closer with CS&S, Open Life Science, 2i2c, The Turing Way, Invest in Open Infrastructure, CSCCE, Talarify, CABANANet, H3ABionet, The Carpentries, Wellcome Trust, Fundación Vía Libre, Conectorial, Centro de Estudios Públicos, and the National Universities of Córdoba and Buenos Aires.</p> <p>We participated in the elaboration of 3 new funding proposals with some of these communities. This proposal was awarded and we are actively looking for funders for this proposal. We also elaborated a new prospectus.</p>	<p>improve our communications engagement.</p> <p>During Year 1, MetaDocencia is establishing solid foundations for the years to come. We are migrating from an almost fully volunteer organization to a 100% funded organization (with 13 active contractors), while designing and documenting all our processes, often from scratch. It is taking us longer than we estimated when we presented this proposal. Nonetheless, due to careful and inclusive governance and culture creation and its implementation, together with thoughtful processes, our team is rapidly attaining high-performance.</p> <p>We are also working intensively to diversify our income and ensure our sustainability after this grant is complete. We are building connections with new funders (e.g., NASA, Sloan Foundation) and submitting new funding proposals. We also now offer consulting services.</p>

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<p>Nurture, guide, and inspire the development of other Global South centered communities of practice for open and reproducible research</p>	<p>Conference participation.</p> <p>MetaDocencia in a Box update.</p> <p>Translation to Portuguese and English infrastructure and workflow setup.</p> <p>Improve functioning and contributors infrastructure.</p> <p>Report our impact.</p> <p>Open access publication (Year 2 milestone)</p>	<p>We participated in two international conferences (ICOTS and CZI Open Science), one local Bioinformatics conference, and were accepted to participate at the Congreso Iberoamericano de Ciencia Abierta.</p> <p>This is the latest version of MetaDocencia in a Box (work still in progress), where a number of citable resources about how we function will be added by the end of 2022.</p> <p>We updated our logo, branding, and communication strategy, including the need to translate some of our work to English so it is accessible to other international communities (e.g., governance event videos, newsletter).</p> <p>To improve the way we measure our impact and increase the probability to contribute to the academic literature, while using data responsibly (e.g., having the approval of an external Ethics Board) we started collaborating with knowledge acquisition researchers at the University of Buenos Aires and are working at designing our impact measurement and publications with them.</p>	<p>Our participation in conferences has been very successful. International and regional conferences are allowing us to further connect with other communities of practice, build alliances, and become visible to new funders.</p> <p>Translating our high-quality production to English increases our chances to become international referents when it comes to generating open source science contextualized materials. Translations to Portuguese of our new workshops will start as soon as the workshop's materials are ready for publication.</p> <p>Setting up contributors' infrastructure is taking longer than expected because of the highly diverse team and community we foster, for whom open contribution platforms such as GitHub are often a barrier. We are working at implementing infrastructure that uses technologies that adapt to people's needs rather than the other way around.</p> <p>We are documenting all our processes and aim to make meaningful, high impact contributions to the academic literature. For us it is key to use all data with the highest responsibility standards.</p>

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